
Fiscal Optimality in Côte d'Ivoire : An approach using Hansen's TAR technique (1999)

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Abstract:

This paper seeks to estimate the optimal tax rate in Côte d'Ivoire over the period 1960-2020. The results of the non-linearity test confirm the evidence of the non-linearity relationship. In addition, the results of the TAR technique proposed by Hansen (1999), show evidence of several tax maxima. Indeed, the optimal tax rate in Côte d'Ivoire is 25.25% of GDP. Beyond this threshold, taxation leads to a reduction in economic activity. These results imply that the levels of economic growth regularly achieved by the Ivorian economy have remained below their potential. These results clearly show that a large part of the Ivorian economy operates in the informal sector.

Keywords: Optimal taxation, Tax revenues, Laffer curve, Economic growth.*

1.Introduction

Since the end of the decade of political and military crisis, the national economy has made undeniable progress. However, it seems to suffer from significant shortcomings in the area of financing. Three instruments have always been used to finance the economy's expenditure (debt policy, monetary policy and fiscal policy). However, the policy of mobilizing fiscal resources remains the most advantageous. Thus, in financing the economy, the state proceeds by means of a compulsory levy on the population. While some researchers argue that taxes improve economic growth, others believe that at a certain level, taxes can degrade economic growth (Keho, 2010 ; Oyibo, 2021).

The Laffer curve illustrates the trade-off between the tax rate and tax revenue : « too much tax kills tax ». Thus, Laffer¹ states that there is a threshold of taxation that minimizes taxpayer welfare losses while maximizing the revenue collected. This statement is the subject of debate in the economic literature. While some researchers believe that there is a maximum from tax revenues, others refute this thesis and support the idea that the Laffer curve can have several maxima (Novales and Ruiz, 2002 ; Bidzo,2016). Other thinkers, such as Fullerton (1982), formally argue that the Laffer curve may not be continuous or have a maximum. These divergences have led to a rise in threshold estimation methods such as the Scully model and the quadratic model which are commonly used. Apart from these models, the use of threshold effect models (TAR², STAR³ etc....) does not escape this context.

In view of all the above, it seems important to ask the question : What is the level of tax pressure that would allow Côte d'Ivoire to maximize its economic growth? This paper aims to examine the optimal tax burden in Côte d'Ivoire through a threshold regression.

Thus, our approach will be articulated around four axes : the first axis will be devoted to the literature review, the second axis will present the econometric approach; the third axis will present our various empirical results and the last axis will take into account the conclusion and the implications of economic policies.

¹ Arthur Laffer of the University of Chicago, although the curve is popularised under his name by Wanniski (1978), was not the designer. Indeed, the existence of this curve illustrating a bell-shaped relationship between tax rates and tax revenues has existed since the 14th century. According to Say (1803), an exaggerated tax destroys the base on which it is levied.

² Threshold Autoregression.

³ Smooth Threshold Autoregression.

2. Literature review

2.1. Optimal taxation theory

Optimal taxation theory represents the search for a tax system that minimises the loss of collective welfare and that respects an exogenous government budget constraint. When a tax is introduced in a market. The "first theorem of welfare theory" shows that any competitive equilibrium is Pareto efficient. If the state cannot perfectly observe all the characteristics of individuals, its intervention in a market will create a distortion that will shift the economic equilibrium towards a sub-optimal state in the Pareto sense. In other words, the use of a 'flat' tax is a priori impossible, the tax instruments and the equilibrium sought are 'second-rate'. We then speak of an 'efficiency criterion' or 'impact criterion' when we seek to minimise this deadweight.

Several theories highlight the optimal tax system in the economic literature. In this section, we will articulate these theories around three basic theories.

- *The theory based on the Ramsey rule*

Tax taxation has been much debated by thinkers so that Ramsey (1927) calls for a structure that is based on the evolution of the tax rate. Ramsey's rule is based on the assumption that markets are assumed to be competitive and without externalities. Thus, the taxation of a good should be in inverse proportion to the compensated elasticity of supply and demand of that good. In other words, Ramsey advocates low taxation for goods with elastic demand and high taxation for goods with inelastic demand. Furthermore, taxation should be proportional to the inverse of price sensitivity in order to create the least possible distortion. However, this theory has limitations as it allows for increased taxation on the budgets of poor households.

- *The income tax theory*

This theory was highlighted by the work of Mirrless (1971). The author applies optimal taxation to income that is the most redistributive. Indeed, it is important for the State to tax individuals with high marginal productivity, as this would lead to a disincentive to work (lower labour supply) and, in turn, to lower tax revenues. The effect of redistribution on social welfare must then be compared with the effect on the labour supply of high productivity individuals and the lost tax revenue. These trade-offs lead to an optimal tax rate. This rate can be determined by threshold effect models.

- *Laffer's theory*

Following Ramsey (1927) and Mirrlees (1971), Laffer (1981) emphasises the stimulation of the supply of goods and services by the state by subsidising companies and reducing their tax burden and that of workers, which he called "tax allergy". Indeed, a tax rate that is too high has negative repercussions on the collection of tax resources, in other words, when the state increases the tax rate, the supposedly rational taxpayer realises that the tax paid is not proportional to the benefit of his tax contribution, hence he will engage in tax avoidance behaviour, also known as "loss of tax citizenship". This concept is explained by the quote "too much tax kills tax". He elaborated his work with a curve that later became known as the Laffer curve. This curve reflects the fact that it is not profitable to set a tax rate above 50% to 80% of GDP.

Fig 1 : Laffer curve

Source : LAFFER (1981)

This curve reflects a bell-shaped or inverted U-shaped relationship between the tax rate and economic growth. Fullerton (1995) found limitations to this curve. For him, it fails to present the optimal tax rate accurately. However, he agrees that there is a relationship between taxation and economic growth. This relationship can have a double-edged effect. Thus, a good tax policy through taxation is a tool for economic growth in that it encourages companies to invest in innovation and human capital. Consequently, it favours job creation and, in turn, a broadening of the tax base (Romer, 1986; Lucas, 1988). Also, a tax policy that is too strict would encourage the development of tax evasion. Laffer's theory is part of the analysis of the overall tax burden of an economy. However, Laffer is only taking up an old idea, already exposed by Ibn Khaldun (1377) and Smith (1776).

2.2. Empirical review

The link between taxation and economic growth has been the subject of several studies in both developed and underdeveloped economies.

Scully (1995) modelled the tax rate in the US over the period 1949 to 1989. He found that the optimal tax rate in the US during this period ranged from 21.5 to 22.9% of GDP. This tax rate will be re-estimated three (3) years later (in 1998) by the same author but this time for the period 1950-1995. He obtained an optimal tax rate of 21% of GDP, i.e. a slight decrease (Scully, 1998). Scully (1996) highlights the existence of threshold effects in New Zealand over the period 1927-1994. The results place the optimal tax rate at around 21% of GDP, with an annual growth rate of 4.8%. Scully (2003) used two different models - Barro and Scully - and concluded that the tax rate that maximises economic growth in the US is 25.1 and 19.3% respectively. Scully (2006) again studied US data (1929-2004), but this time using his own methodology developed in 1996, and concluded that the optimal tax rate is 23% of GDP.

Incidentally, an earlier study was conducted by Saibu (2015) in determining the tax rate for the Nigerian and South African cases using a Scully model. The time series data used for the Nigerian case covers the period 1970 to 2012 and that of the South African case from 1964 to 2012. The results obtained by the author support the conclusion that the tax rate of the Nigerian economy is sub-optimal while that of the South African economy is over-optimal. In both cases, the two economies face difficulties in mobilising more domestic resources for their financing. For the case of North Africa, Salah et echaoui (2018) modelled the fiscal pressure in Morocco with annual data over the period 1985 to 2016 through the augmented Scully model. He then shows that the observed tax burden is above its optimal threshold of 22.4% of GDP. The studies of Yawovi and Amedanou (2019) on the determination of the optimal tax burden in Togo during the period 1960 to 2016, lead to the results that the optimal tax burden of the Togolese economy is 22.6% of GDP.

A study was conducted in Togo by Yawovi and Amedanou (2019). Using annual data over the period 1960 to 2016, their research finds that the optimal tax burden in the Togolese economy is 22.6% of GDP. These results are obtained using the augmented Scully and augmented quadratic models as the authors state that the non-linear relationship between taxation and economic activity can be influenced by other control variables such as private investment, the primary deficit and gross domestic product per capita and gross fixed capital formation. According to our authors, African economies are characterised by their left-hand positions on the Laffer curve.

With regard to the Ivorian economy, (Keho, 2010) through the Scully model and the quadratic model, finds respective tax pressure rates of 21 and 23.5% of GDP during the period 1960-2004. In line with Keho, Oyibo (2021), using Scully's model, finds a fiscal optimum of 34.6% of GDP. In any case, both studies argue that the fiscal optimum has not yet been reached in Côte d'Ivoire.

Fig 2 : Transmission channels of Laffer's theory

Source : Oyibo (2021)

3. Methodology

3.1. Theoretical model

The existence of non-linear relationships between economic and financial variables abounds in the economic literature today. Economic growth is an objective sought by most developing countries. Therefore, taxation is recommended to meet financing needs. However, based on Laffer's theory of optimal taxation, and empirical work by Keho (2010), Moltoja (2016), Salah & Abdellah (2018) and Yawovi (2018), who have shown the existence of a Laffer curve of growth, we adopt a threshold effect technique.

The model used in this study is a threshold model of the autoregressive net transition type (TAR) of Hansen (1999). This model makes it possible to identify the critical threshold(s) in the relationship between fiscal pressure and economic growth, unlike the Scully model and the quadratic model which have a single maxima. Indeed, this technique, unlike the threshold autoregressive models (TAR) proposed by Tong (1990) and the smooth autoregressive transition (STAR) model proposed by Terasvirta (1994), allows for the explanation of non-linearity in a simple framework and allows for different dynamics across regimes. The TAR specifications are easy to estimate and interpret.

The model is formulated as follows:

$$Y_t = \theta_1 X_t I(q_t \leq \gamma) + \theta_2 X_t I(q_t > \gamma) + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

With $I(.)$ the indicator function. Thus we can reformulate it by the following equation:

$$Y_t \begin{cases} \theta_{11} X_t + \varepsilon_t & q_t \leq \gamma \\ \theta_{21} X_t + \varepsilon_t & q_t > \gamma \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

With: Y_t : the dependent variable ; X_t : the vector of independent variables; q_t : the transition variable; γ : the threshold value; ε_t : the residuals of the estimation. Thus, $q_t \in X_t$: This means that the transition variable can be one of the elements of the vector of independent variables and its distribution is assumed to be continuous

3.2. Empirical model

In this study, we explain economic growth, which will be approximated by the logarithm of GDP (LGDP), and tax revenue as a percentage of GDP (TAX), which will be used as a proxy for taxation. Referring to the literature, we have included in our model control variables such as gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) as a proxy for investment and population growth (POP_GR). All the data used in this section come from the World Bank database (WDI 2021) and the website of the Central Bank of West African States (CBWA). The data cover the period 1960 to 2020.

The empirical equation is as follows:

$$LGDP_t = \begin{cases} \alpha_{11}TAX_t + \alpha_{12}GFCF_t + \alpha_{13}POP_GR_t + \varepsilon_t & q_t \leq \gamma \\ \alpha_{21}TAX_t + \alpha_{22}GFCF_t + \alpha_{23}POP_GR_t + \varepsilon_t & q_t > \gamma \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

With γ : the threshold value and q_t : the Tax.

4. Empirical results

The non-linearity test with Tax Pressure as the transition variable, states that there is a non-linear relationship between taxation and the level of economic activity. Indeed, the critical value at the 5% threshold is higher than the scaled F-stat only from the transition from the second to the third regime. Moreover, this test reveals the existence of three critical thresholds whose values will be determined in the estimation of our model.

Table 1 : Non-linearity test

Sequential F-statistic determined thresholds: 2			
		Scaled	Critical
Threshold Test	F-statistic	F-statistic	Value**
0 vs. 1 *	28.4083	113.6332	16.19
1 vs. 2 *	9.9992	39.9969	18.11
2 vs. 3	2.0701	8.2805	18.93

Source : Author, based on data from BCEAO (2021) and WDI (2021)

The estimation results obtained using the Eviews 12 software are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2 : Estimation results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
PF < 17.3047 -- 31 obs				
Constant	23.0331***	0.5001	46.0568	0.0000
Tax	0.1020*	0.0526	1.9375	0.0585
Gross fixed capital formation	0.0374***	0.0080	4.6711	0.0000
Population growth	-0.2206*	0.1127	-1.9581	0.0559
17.3047 <= PF < 25.2551 -- 21 obs				
Constant	21.2911***	0.5324	39.989	0.0000
Tax	0.1450***	0.0299	4.8425	0.0000
Gross fixed capital formation	-0.0778***	0.0114	-6.7707	0.0000
Population growth	0.0810	0.2223	0.3647	0.7169
25.2551 <= PF -- 9 obs				
Constant	21.1463***	1.1296	18.7191	0.0000
Tax	-0.0137**	0.0160	-0.8547	0.0469
Gross fixed capital formation	0.0510*	0.0280	1.8165	0.0754
Population growth	0.3847	0.3333	1.1541	0.2540
Adjusted R-squared	0.8659	Durbin-Watson stat		1.2876
<i>Note : *** : P-value<0.01 ; ** : P-value<0.05 ; * : P-value<0.1.</i>				

Source : Author, based on data from BCEAO (2021) and WDI (2021)

Let the equation be :

$$LGDP_t = \begin{cases} 0.1020TAX_t + 0.0374GFCE_t - 0.2206POP_GR_t + 23.0331 & q_t \leq 17.3047 \\ 0.1450TAX_t - 0.0778GFCE_t + 0.0810POP_GR_t + 21.2911 & 17.3047 \leq q_t < 25.2551 \\ -0.0137TAX_t + 0.0510GFCE_t + 0.3847POP_GR_t + 21.1463 & 25.2551 < q_t \end{cases} \quad (1.20)$$

If we consider Certurus paribus, the results obtained show the existence of two critical thresholds, hence the existence of three regimes.

In the first regime, the relationship between tax pressure and economic activity, in particular the logarithm of GDP, remains positive as long as the tax pressure does not exceed the threshold of 17.30% of GDP with a low associated elasticity of 0.10. Specifically, growth increases by

0.01% if the tax rate increases by 1%. However, during the period 1960 to 2020, this threshold was exceeded 31 times. Similarly, gross fixed capital formation has a positive and significant influence on the logarithm of GDP. In other words, a 1% increase in gross fixed capital formation leads to a 0.03% increase in the logarithm of GDP. The effect of the population growth rate on the logarithm of GDP is significantly negative at the 10% level. This could be explained by the fact that population growth is not followed by an increase in the level of education (human capital).

In the second regime, the tax burden seems to have a stronger positive impact on economic growth when it oscillates between 17.30 and 25.25% of GDP. Indeed, the elasticity associated with the tax burden is 0.14. In this regime, the gross fixed capital formation has a negative and significant influence on the logarithm of GDP, where a 1% increase in the gross fixed capital formation leads to a 0.07% decrease in economic activity. However, population growth has a positive but insignificant influence on the logarithm of GDP.

In the third regime, the tax burden seems to have a negative impact on economic activity when it remains above the threshold of 25.25% of GDP. More precisely, growth is reduced by 0.013% if the tax burden increases by 1% while respecting the conditions of the regime (tax burden between 17.30 and 25.25% of GDP). Gross fixed capital formation has a positive and significant impact, the logarithm of GDP increases by 0.05% if investment increases by 1%. Population growth has a positive but insignificant effect on the logarithm of GDP.

Thus, these results are in line with those obtained by Keho (2010) and Oyibo (2021), which show that the Ivorian economy is currently positioned towards the left-hand side of the Laffer curve. Moreover, the tax burden seems to have a negative impulse when it exceeds the critical threshold of 25.25% with a low elasticity of (-0.01). Econometrically, the model is globally well specified with an adjusted R-squared = 0.86. These results therefore confirm the non-linear relationship between the tax burden and economic growth.

In the following, we will perform diagnostic tests to see if the model is well specified. The results are shown in the table below:

Table 3 : Summary of diagnostic tests on residues

Purpose	Test	Test statistics	P-value	Conclusion
Autocorrelation	Breusch Godfrey Serial LM Test	$nR^2 = 2.6149$	0.0657	Not autocorrelation
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pargan- Godfrey	$nR^2 = 2.0830$	0.1009	Not heteroscedasticity
Normality	Jarque Bera	$JB = 3.0241$	0.2204	Normal distribution

Source : Author, based on data from BCEAO (2021) and WDI (2021)

The p-values of the different tests are above the 5% significance level. This indicates that all tests performed were significant. Therefore, it seems reasonable to conclude that the residuals satisfy the assumptions of the classical normal linear regression model

Fig 3 : Cusum and Cusum of squares Tests

Source : Author, based on data from BCEAO (2021) and WDI (2021)

Finally, the tests of stability of the estimated model make it possible to confirm this. Indeed, both versions of this test, namely the CUSUM, based on the cumulative sum of recursive residuals, and the CUSUM SQ, based on the cumulative sum of the square of recursive residuals, are conclusive.

5. Conclusion

This study examines the fiscal optimum in Côte d'Ivoire using a threshold regression (TAR) of Hansen (1999). The results of the non-linearity test confirm the existence of three regimes. In other words, the Laffer curve hypothesis is verified for the Ivorian economy. Furthermore, the estimation results reveal that above 25.25% of GDP, taxation reduces economic growth. However, this optimum is much higher than the actual tax burden in 2019 (18.12% of GDP). Also, we find that this threshold is higher than the one determined by Keho (2010) by the Schully model and the quadratic model which was equal to 21.1% of GDP. In view of these results, the inefficiency of the Ivorian tax system in mobilising more resources to finance the needs of the economy is evident. Furthermore, despite the Ivorian government's continuous efforts to implement effective poverty reduction policies, tax revenue mobilisation strategies remain ineffective. This could be explained by the staggering expansion of the informal sector.

The policy implications of this research are twofold. First, economic policies should be adopted to facilitate the formalisation of informal production units. Second, the implementation of fiscal incentive policies (tax exemptions, easier access to bank loans, etc.) with the need to integrate all decentralised local governments is a wise strategy.

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